

Novel Heuristic Parameters in Coronary Artery Disease Prevention – Theoretical Equations and Considerations

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Abstract

Many factors are associated with the incidence and progression of coronary artery disease. Still, the exact mechanisms and pathophysiology are not clearly understood. The process of atherosclerosis remains an enigma, though some basic mechanisms and pathophysiology are known. There are some risk factors associated with some clinical conditions, which appear protective based on the clinical experience. Heuristically, the weightage and performance are represented by the equations. The factors include chronic obstructive lung disease, chronic liver diseases, cataract formation, and chronic renal failure, where the incidence and progression are slower. However, further mechanisms like hypoxic-ischemic growth factors – collateral formation, Estrogen - VEGF, dystrophic calcification mechanisms, and parathyroid hormone or calcium-related metabolism through 1,25 dihydroxy cholecalciferol could play an active role in etiopathogenesis respectively. Understanding and utilizing the underlying pathophysiology and mechanisms can be highly productive in the prevention, progression, and treatment of coronary artery disease.

Main text

There are many factors which influence the onset and incidence of coronary artery disease. Apart from the conventional risk factors numerous other factors influence the occurrence of coronary artery disease. Some of the factors are unexplained and though not subtle possibly play a role in the incidence and progression of coronary artery disease. In the heuristic assessment of these factors, some factors could include presence of chronic respiratory disorders, chronic liver disease, cataract formation and chronic kidney disease. The underlying mechanisms

could be hypoxia and hypoxic growth factors, estrogen and vascular endothelial growth factors, dystrophic calcification mechanisms and parathyroid hormones or associated mechanisms respectively. Though coronary artery calcifications are associated with higher incidence of coronary artery disease the concept is not well studied especially in its association with cardiovascular mortality. The association of cataract and cardiovascular disorders have not been studied in depth though some studies are associated with higher association of cataract with cardiovascular diseases.^{1,2} Chronic liver diseases are associated with higher levels of estrogen and estrogen is known to prevent occurrence of coronary diseases in premenopausal women.³ Estrogen is also associated with lesser calcification in coronary vessels.^{4,5} Hypoparathyroidism⁶ and Hyperparathyroidism as seen in chronic renal diseases⁷ are associated with coronary artery disorders. The progression of coronary artery disease after the onset is usually slow compared to other general parameters, in the opinion of the author. Dense coronary calcifications are often difficult to treat, and at times require atherectomy or rotator devices during coronary angioplasty.

One possible mechanism could be the calcification of vulnerable plaques.⁸ Chronic calcific coronary diseases can be associated with coronary collaterals formation, and the underlying coronary capillary circulation cannot be studied easily. Estrogen per se is associated with lesser coronary events in females in premenopausal women but due to thrombotic phenomenon and malignancy potential it cannot be used as a therapy for preventive purposes in postmenopausal age group. Instead, estrogen associated molecules like digoxin in very low doses can iterate the benefits. Similarly, calcification induction mechanisms can be triggered to induce dystrophic calcifications in a graded or therapeutic manner using parathyroid hormone or vitamin D or its derivative molecules.

Cataracts can be associated with cardiovascular morbidity.¹ However, the progression and mortality reasons are still not clear by literature. There are some observations where coronary artery calcification could be beneficial which can be seen in stable angina and less or no calcifications more commonly associated with myocardial infarction.⁸⁻¹³ Especially the calcium density is associated with the protection effect.⁸ Intense physical activity is associated with higher calcification which is observed paradoxically.¹⁴

Many published studies show an increased association between chronic obstructive lung disease (COPD) and coronary artery disease.^{15,16} However, in the experience of the author an inverse correlation is observed between COPD and coronary artery disease manifestation. There is lack of convincing evidence that frequent exacerbations of COPD are association with acute coronary events.¹⁵

However, the concepts are preliminary. Further research is required to study the benefits of these parameters' vs incidence of acute coronary events or cardiovascular mortality. These parameters can be tapped for therapeutic purposes by easy application in clinical practice, if the research outcomes are suggestive.

The equations presented are heuristically written by the author based on clinical and bedside observations and experience, which require experimental evaluation/validation in the future.

The equations (Supplement 1) are solved in the following method in Wolfram,

Where $y = x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4$

x_1 is the presence of chronic lung diseases, x_2 – chronic liver diseases, x_3 - cataract formation and x_4 - chronic renal diseases

In the equations:

$x_1 = x + x(\sin\theta)$, $x_2 = x\sqrt{(\sin\theta)}$, $x_3 = x + x\sqrt{(\cos\theta)}$, $x_4 = x + x(\sin\theta)^{1/3}$

Author contribution

The author conceived the idea, equations and wrote the paper.

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